

THE ROLE OF LAW ENFORCEMENT AUTHORITIES IN THE FIGHT AGAINST EXTREMISM AND IDIOLOGY

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Abstract. *Representatives of each field will be discussed about their main tasks and cooperation related to terrorism and religious extremism, which is one of the areas of activity.*

Keywords: *fanaticism, terrorism and extremism, internal affairs bodies, the main activity of a number of services, patriotism.*

Today, combating the scourge of fanaticism, terrorism and extremism is defined as the main activity of a number of services of internal affairs bodies.

The main tasks and cooperation of representatives of each field related to terrorism and religious extremism, which is one of the areas of activity, are defined in the relevant normative legal documents of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. Internal affairs bodies cooperate with law enforcement agencies in order to effectively organize activities related to terrorism and religious extremism and to achieve positive results in this direction. In carrying out activities on terrorism and religious extremism, it is of particular importance to organize cooperation of internal affairs bodies, first of all, with sectoral services. It is organized based on the requirements of the regulatory legal documents of the regulatory bodies.

If we pay attention to the fight against terrorism, we see that international cooperation is implemented in several directions. Criminal acts defined as dangerous and illegal for the society of states are recognized as terrorist acts, regardless of who and where they are committed. Because this danger affects the interests of not one, but two or more countries, that is, if such acts are committed on the territory of foreign countries, citizens of other countries also become their victims.

In order to effectively ensure large-scale cooperation in the fight against terrorism and extremism, it is necessary to organize, coordinate and manage this cooperation.

After all, President Shavkat Mirziyoev said, "Currently, in the world, opposition and conflicts between different forces are increasing, there is a fierce struggle for resources. There are new threats to peace and security in our region" [1, p.371].

As defined in the regulatory legal documents, organization, coordination and management of cooperation between the sectoral services of internal affairs bodies at the district and city level, as well as their cooperation with the public, is carried out by the following persons:

a) cooperation management - by the head of the district, city internal affairs department (department) and his deputies;

b) coordination of cooperation - by the head of the department (division) of the department (department) of the district, city internal affairs department (department) of the Combating Terrorism and Extremism (CT and E);

v) organization of cooperation - by senior operational representatives of CT and E department.

The head of the internal affairs department (department) is the highest person responsible for managing large-scale cooperation in CT and E at the district, city level.

Management of cooperation on the basis of CT and E is the activity of issuing executive orders by authorized state bodies and officials on the organizational-methodical, legal, material and technical provision of cooperation between the employees of the internal affairs bodies and the public on the basis of CT and E is considered

It should be noted that the boundaries of the territory served by CT and E and the operative (senior) representatives serving in them are determined by the head of the city and district IIB in agreement with the mayors of the said city or district on the scale of the neighborhood.

The monthly work plan drawn up by immediate (senior) representatives is approved by the head of the city, district Ministry of Internal Affairs or his first deputy.

The cooperative activities of CT and E are discussed at monthly, quarterly, half-yearly and year-end meetings in the presence of the head of the city, district IIB or one of his deputies. Specific measures will be determined in order to eliminate identified shortcomings and improve the efficiency of work in this regard in the future.

In these meetings, a representative (senior) will provide information about the shortcomings made in cooperation with the work on the fight against and prevention of terrorism-related crimes, as well as about the employees who regularly violated service discipline during the cooperation, deviated from the set routes and achieved low performance, and came to help. and, in necessary cases, makes reasonable proposals for disciplinary punishment and, if necessary, dismissal from the positions held by employees who grossly violated service discipline during cooperation.

An important aspect of the head of the district, city internal affairs department (management) in managing the activities of CT and E and the large-scale cooperation based on them is the organizational-methodical and material-technical work aimed at the effective organization and improvement of this activity or cooperation, and the elimination of identified problems and shortcomings. makes management decisions and supervises their implementation. This is an integral part of managing the activities of CT and E and the large-scale cooperation based on them - it serves to provide legal support.

In addition, the reception and transfer of the service area by the employee appointed to the position of the operational (senior) representative of CT and E is carried out with the direct participation of the head of the city, district internal affairs office, his first deputy or the head of the department of CT and E.

The head of the district, city internal affairs department (management) in most cases, on the basis of CT and E, manages the mutual cooperation of the employees of the sectoral services of the internal affairs bodies, as well as their cooperation with the public through his deputies.

In the system of district and city internal affairs bodies, implementation of rapid search activities based on CT and E, solving committed crimes, identifying and arresting wanted persons, combating terrorism and religious extremism, in particular, implementation of rapid activities for this purpose. large-scale cooperation is managed by the first deputy head of the department (department) of internal affairs.

Powers of state bodies and non-governmental organizations. According to the current regulatory legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the main responsibility for managing

cooperation based on CT and E is assigned to the deputy head of the district, city internal affairs department (administration), who heads the preventive service.

It is necessary to use the capabilities of agencies working in different directions to solve the crime of terrorism and extremism. Therefore, in this case, there is a need to ensure close cooperation between some units. One of the most important issues to be solved by the chief as he organizes cooperation in solving crimes of terrorism and extremism is the establishment of a system of mutual information exchange. It represents an existing specific information center (bank) that serves as a unique dispatching point for the distribution of information as needed and at the request of cooperating services and units. The task is to ensure familiarization of services and departments with the types of information in the data bank: to constantly fill the information set with new information; according to the requests of the interested services, it is to provide the information necessary for them in a timely manner. For this purpose, to determine the procedures for sending and receiving relevant information from duty units to services and divisions, to ensure the development of appropriate forms of documents (requests, information carriers); it is necessary to ensure timely changes to existing documents (model plans, calculations, etc.). The organization of such a system of mutual information exchange allows to ensure the timely exchange of necessary information with the cooperating service, makes it easier to solve the crime and search for the criminal.

The chief's organization of solving crimes by working on hot leads does not end there. He takes personal responsibility for all the stages of ensuring this field of work, that is, up to sending the criminal case to court. If it is not possible to solve the crime in the first days after the commission of the crime, the chief should ensure that complex measures are taken for each possible incident, critically evaluate the results of the previously developed plans, determine and organize the implementation of additional investigation and rapid search measures. ; should regularly monitor their implementation.

In particular, the activity of the chief to organize the investigation of crimes at the next stages is represented by the time factor. The situation is also complicated by the fact that the employees are working on solving newly committed crimes. It should be noted that the activity of the units is evaluated based on the number of crimes registered in previous years. Despite the fact that in statistical reports a separate line (graph) is allocated to the indicators of the detection of crimes over the past years, in practice this is not actually taken into account and does not affect the overall assessment of the work of internal affairs agencies. In such conditions, it is natural that the activity of the employees in solving crimes will decrease, they will not be solved, and the number of such crimes will increase.

At this stage of solving the crimes of terrorism and extremism, the head should ensure the succession of the previous measures and organizational forms of cooperation in the organization of cooperation between services and units. The main efforts of the participants of cooperation should be focused on the search for information about the crime being committed (committed) and the circumstances of the persons involved in it. The initiative to implement this or that measure must come from the investigator conducting the criminal case. This does not mean that the head himself does not propose this initiative.

Cooperation does not end if the person who committed the crime is identified. In this context, the tasks of the participants of the cooperation will be to gain comprehensiveness, to fully

identify all the circumstances defining the subject of proof in the criminal case, to identify and expose all the participants of the crime, to prove all aspects of their criminal activity.

Cooperation should continue until the investigation is completed. It is necessary to manage the intensity of cooperative investigative efforts and search and rescue measures, taking into account the achieved results. After the participants of the cooperation have taken drastic measures to solve the crime, a decision is made to stop the cooperation according to the proposal of the head of the investigative-operational group.

During the organization of cooperation in solving crimes, the efforts of the participants of joint activities are to collect, systematize and collect information on unsolved criminal cases, establish contact with the operatives of the JIB and use their capabilities, use public representatives, use the capabilities of the mass media and focused on the implementation of complex measures on etc. For this purpose, a special operative group is formed and it is the main organizational link for solving such crimes.

The stability of the composition of such groups, the uniformity of the work performed by them, the planning of the activities of each member of the group, constant control over their activities, practical and methodical support should be ensured.

The cooperation with the operational services of the special operational-investigative group of the Department of Criminal Affairs, investigative detention center (IDC), temporary storage room (TSR), rehabilitation centers gives positive results. It is also important to ensure the study of other information of interest in criminal cases in the archive on similar crimes.

Analysis of crime, unsolved crimes (type of crimes, place and method of their commission, object of criminal aggression, methods of concealment of crime, etc.) plays an important role in ensuring cooperation of members of the special specialized operative-investigative team.

Investigations are an integral part of the fight against crime. Among the unsearched criminals, dangerous criminals occupy a significant place, and it should be noted that there are serious shortcomings in the activities in this direction. One of the reasons for such situations is the poor organization of local organizations. City and district leaders of internal affairs agencies pay little attention to the search for criminals, do not thoroughly study the reasons for bad searches, do not ensure the full use of forces and means in the search for criminals, and their cooperation at the required level.

All services and units must be involved in the search for a hidden criminal. Organization of these works is entrusted to the city-district heads. It is they who must ensure the wide use of the powers and means of the specified bodies. They are entrusted with the responsibility of organizing the cooperation of these forces, as well as cooperation with certain internal affairs agencies (with the approval of senior leaders).

The main volume of search operations is carried out by CT and E units. Therefore, when organizing cooperation, they are usually appointed to be responsible for the implementation of one or another search activity in cooperation.

City-district heads in the organization of cooperation should ensure effective use of opportunities unique to each of the partners in search in various forms and methods of work, provide them with practical assistance, carry out constant control over the implementation of search measures, study best practices in search and should spread.

The choice of the forms of organization of such cooperation should be made taking into account the characteristics of the crime committed by the wanted person, the circumstances of his

person's escape, and the capabilities of the participants of the cooperation. In any case, the attention and efforts of the participants of cooperation: to identify and study the lifestyle and behavior of the wanted person, his relatives and acquaintances, and the persons with whom he had a relationship or who helped him to hide; in the places where it is likely to appear, to register the persons coming and going to this address, to carry out continuous operational surveillance in order to recognize the wanted person based on his appearance, photo or behavioral signs; conducting secret or disguised inspections of his former residence and the residences of his relatives and other close people; conducting surveillance in places where the wanted person is likely to appear; to influence relatives and acquaintances of the wanted person in order to convince him to bear his guilt; checking existing accounts etc.

According to the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Combating Terrorism" (this law was amended on April 30, 2004 and with amendments that came into force on July 6, 2004).

Article 6. Assistance to the state bodies implementing the fight against terrorism.

State management bodies, local government bodies, citizens' self-government bodies, public associations, enterprises, institutions and organizations, officials, as well as citizens assist and provide necessary assistance to state bodies implementing the fight against terrorism.

Article 7. International cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan in the fight against terrorism.

Cooperation of the Republic of Uzbekistan with foreign countries, their law enforcement agencies, special services and international organizations in the field of combating terrorism is carried out in accordance with the international agreements of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Persons guilty of violations of anti-terrorism legislation shall be held accountable in accordance with the established procedure.

Article 8. State bodies for the fight against terrorism.

The state bodies implementing the fight against terrorism are as follows:

- State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- National Guard of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- State security service of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Internal Affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- State Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Ministry of Emergency Situations of the Republic of Uzbekistan;
- Department of Combating Economic Crimes under the General Prosecutor's Office of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

The State Security Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan shall coordinate the activities of the state bodies involved in the fight against terrorism and ensure that they work together to prevent, identify, put an end to, and minimize the consequences of terrorist activities.

Ensuring legality, rights and freedoms of citizens and their legitimate interests in the fight against terrorism and extremism; constant rapid readiness; targeted and effective implementation of the events; effective and comprehensive conduct of overt and undercover rapid-search forces, tools and activities; it is carried out in strict compliance with the principles of close cooperation with other ministries, departments, enterprises, institutions, organizations and the public

Today, in a situation where many countries of the world are facing serious problems of various forms, the life of our people is improving day by day as a result of the reforms implemented

consistently in all fields by our respected President during the past thirty-two years of independence, especially in the conditions of New Uzbekistan. Here, President Shavkat Mirziyoev said in his speech at the 78th session of the UN General Assembly on September 19, 2023: "Development of human capital and training of creative young generation is one of the strategic tasks that Uzbekistan has set before itself. We consider open and high-quality education for everyone to be the most effective factor for eradicating poverty, improving people's well-being and achieving sustainable economic growth" [2, p.1-2.], he noted. The essence of this is to invite a person to a deeper understanding of his human factor in life and his inner potential. Therefore, we will solve the above-mentioned problems by educating young people with knowledge.

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